

Adsorption of Benzol Vapour by Mixed Adsorbents.

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In a previous paper (Chowdhury and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 122) it was shown that specially prepared mixed adsorbents had a very high adsorption capacity and this fact was utilized for the desulphurisation of mineral oils. It is now intended to study the properties of the mixed adsorbents further with a view to find a suitable adsorbent for benzol and also to extend the study of mixed adsorbents to bauxite, a mineral, which owing to its physical properties, particularly its hardness, is preferred as an adsorbent in several industries. Artificial adsorbents such as silica gel and activated carbon are liable to crumble to very fine dust on repeated use. Activated carbon though characterised by its high adsorption capacity for benzol hydrocarbons, is pyrophorous in nature, and hence liable to catch fire, specially when heat is evolved in the course of adsorption. This property makes its regeneration by the simple process of roasting in an oxidising atmosphere impossible. It is therefore of great interest to investigate if a substitute could be found in a hard mineral like bauxite, which occurs in India in extensive deposits within easy reach of the larger coke-ovens and can be obtained at a nominal cost.

The determination of adsorption capacity was made by the dynamic method, in preference to the static method, as the former is simpler from experimental point of view and corresponds more closely to the large scale practice. The following arrangement was used for the purpose :

Dry air was passed at a constant rate of 180 c.c. per minute through a double-walled vessel *B*, containing a definite amount of benzol and placed in a thermostat *C*. The benzolised air then passed through a coil surrounding the adsorption vessel *A* (Fig. I), which was placed within a wider tube, entering it at the bottom. The temperature of both the vessels *A* and *B* were kept constant, usually at 26°, by means of the thermostat, the coil serving to bring

the gas to the same temperature before adsorption actually took place. The adsorption tube was attached to the coil by means of ground-glass joint and could be detached and weighed before and after each adsorption. Concentration of benzol vapour in the air could be changed if necessary by regulating the temperature of the thermostat and the rate of flow. If desired, fresh air might also be mixed with the benzolised air, as it came out of the vessel *B*. In each case the vapour was passed until the weight of the adsorbent was practically constant.

Fig. I.

Adsorption by Artificially Prepared Mixed Adsorbents.

The following mixed adsorbents were prepared and their activities studied with the help of the arrangement described above.

- (1) Mixed alumina and activated carbon.
- (2) Mixed alumina and silica gels.
- (3) Mixed alumina and ferric oxide gels.

Mixed alumina and activated Carbon.—The mixed adsorbent was prepared by precipitating alumina on finely divided activated carbon followed by washing and drying, and finally activated by heating in a current of air to 220–280° in an electric furnace.

The percentage of the components of the mixed adsorbent was varied and their adsorption capacities ascertained. These are noted in the following table and graphically shewn in Fig. II, Curve 1.

TABLE I.

Size of the particles = 30–60 mesh. Temperature = 26°.

Concentration of benzol vapour in air = 1.2 per cent. by vol.

Rate of air flow = 180 c. c. per minute.

Percentage of Al_2O_3 in the mixture.	Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt. of adsorbent.	Increase of weight.	Percentage of adsorption.
100	3.5124 g.	3.6412 g.	0.1288 g.	3.67
64.7	4.124	4.8606	0.7366	17.96
51.8	2.589	3.415	0.826	31.90
41.4	2.2218	3.111	0.8892	40.03
6.73	0.2586	0.3066	0.1378	53.246
0	0.3305	0.4994	0.1689	51.10

It will be observed that alumina gel has a very slight activity (3.67%) as compared to activated carbon (51.1%), and only a slight increase in the adsorption capacity is obtained by the mixture containing 6.73 per cent. of Al_2O_3 . Deposition of inorganic gels on activated carbon makes it, however, less inflammable (Berl, D. R.-P. 375658).

(2) *Mixed alumina and silica gels.*—The mixed adsorbent was prepared by suspending aluminium hydroxide in sodium silicate solution and adding hydrochloric acid under constant stirring until the solution was slightly alkaline, stirring being continued until silica gel completely precipitated. The mixed precipitate was then activated by heating to 220–230° in an electric furnace in a current of dry air. The proportion of the components was varied by taking different amounts of sodium silicate from a stock solution of known strength. The results obtained with different percentages of alumina are shown in the following table (Fig. II, Curve II).

Effect of Composition on Adsorption Capacity.

Fig. II.

- I—Adsorption of benzol by mixed alumina and activated carbon.
 II— " " " " " silica gel.
 III— " " " " " ferric oxide gel.

TABLE II.

Experimental conditions same as in Table I.

Percentage of alumina in the adsorbent.	Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt. of adsorbent.	Increase of weight.	Percentage of adsorption.
0	3.556 g.	3.903 g.	0.347 g.	9.76
21.8	0.156	0.1816	0.0256	16.41
27.9	0.521	0.6263	0.1053	20.21
35.2	0.1175	0.1357	0.0182	15.48
39.46	0.1123	0.1262	0.016	14.25
100	3.5124	3.6412	0.1288	3.67

Mixed alumina and ferric oxide gels.—The mixed adsorbent was prepared by taking different amounts of ferric and aluminium sulphates from their stock solutions of known strength in a beaker

and precipitating their hydroxides simultaneously in the usual manner. The mass was carefully washed, dried and activated as in the previous case. The iron content of the mixed adsorbent was determined volumetrically by titration with potassium dichromate. The results of the experiments are shown in the following table and in Curve III, Fig. II. As in previous cases the adsorption reaches a maximum (14.29 per cent.) with definite percentages of Fe_2O_3 in the mixture, while pure alumina gel adsorbs 3.67 per cent. and ferric oxide gel 7.2 per cent. only under the same conditions. The increase in adsorption is, however, smaller than the previous instance.

TABLE III.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Percentage of Al_2O_3 in the mixture.	Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt. of adsorbent.	Increase of weight.	Percentage of adsorption.
0	1.841 g.	1.4876 g.	0.0866 g.	7.2
22.7	0.8618	0.9496	0.0878	10.19
56.9	1.4062	1.6072	0.2010	14.29
61.1	0.2376	0.9152	0.0776	9.26
75.8	0.9492	0.9904	0.0412	4.34
100	3.5124	3.6412	0.1288	3.67

It may be noted that this rise in the activity of mixed adsorbents is observed only when they are formed by simultaneous precipitation or by the formation of one adsorbent in the pores of the other. Mechanical mixtures, however intimately they might be mixed together, show no increased activity.

Bauxite as an Adsorbent for Benzol Vapour.

Having determined the properties of mixed alumina and ferric oxide gels, it is now intended to study the properties of bauxite which is a natural mixed adsorbent composed mainly of alumina and ferric oxide. Bauxite has been used for a long time as an adsorbent in petroleum industry. It has been found that some bauxites are highly active while others are comparatively inert and no satisfactory explanation has so far been put forward to explain this difference. It is well known that the adsorption capacity of bauxite does not depend on its alumina content or on any other component. In the light of the following experiments it will be seen that the adsorption

capacity of bauxite corresponds very closely to that of mixed adsorbents and depends on a suitable proportion of Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 contents. It is likely that one adsorbent is formed in the pores of the others, thus increasing the number of very fine capillary pores which would naturally enhance the activity.

Bauxite used in these experiments gave the following analytical data:—

Al_2O_3	...	69.15 per cent.	SiO_2	...	0.91
Fe_2O_3	...	28.2	TiO_2	...	1.5

The mineral was powdered and heated to $330\text{--}350^\circ$ in a current of dry air for two hours and cooled before its adsorption capacity was determined. The concentration of benzol vapour in the gas was varied and the results obtained are noted in the following table and shown graphically in Fig. III.

Adsorption Isotherm with Bauxite as Adsorbent (26°).

Fig. III.

TABLE IV.

Conditions same as in Table I,

Percentage of benzol in air by vol.	Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.	Amount adsorbed per g.
0.79	0.3326 g.	0.3524 g.	0.0198 g.	5.95	0.0595
1.2	1.351	1.4648	0.1138	8.42	0.0842
2.3	0.1648	0.2092	0.0244	13.2	0.132
3.9	0.2026	0.284	0.0814	15.49	0.1548

It will be observed that the adsorption varies with concentration as is to be expected from Freundlich's equation, the curve being of the nature of a parabola.

The adsorption figures for bauxite are considerably higher than those of either alumina gel or ferric oxide gel, but on the whole are lower than those of the mixed alumina and ferric oxide gels prepared in the laboratory. This is however, only to be expected in view of difference in the conditions of formation of the two adsorbents. When the concentration of benzol in the air corresponds to that in which it is generally present in coal or coke-oven gas (0.79 per cent. by vol.), the adsorption comes to only 5.95 per cent. which is rather too low a figure for the large scale application of bauxite. The following experiments represent attempts to investigate if bauxite could be activated further with a view to make its industrial application as an adsorbent for benzol possible.

Activation of Bauxite.

(a) *Activation of bauxite by deposition of ferric oxide gel.*—The first idea that suggests itself for the activation of bauxite is to deposit ferric oxide gel on it so as to bring up its iron content to correspond to the amount found most suitable in the mixed alumina and ferric oxide gels. For this purpose finely divided bauxite was suspended in a solution of ferric sulphate, and ferric hydroxide was precipitated in the usual manner under constant stirring. This was washed, dried and activated at 330–350°. The results of adsorption are noted in the following table.

TABLE V.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Percentage composition of adsorbent in the mixture :		Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .				
51.9	48.1	0.4788 g.	0.5256 g.	0.0618	10.98
47.6	45.6	1.2108	1.8718	0.161	13.3
38.9	58.5	1.3508	0.5102	0.1594	11.8

It will be observed from the above table that as in the case of mixed adsorbent, the activity of bauxite increases with the increase of ferric oxide content until the latter reaches 47.6 per cent. when it adsorbs 13.3 per cent. of benzol; the maximum in the case of mixed

alumina-ferric oxide gels with 43.1 per cent. of ferric oxide (or 56.9 per cent. of alumina) being 14.29 per cent. The following data show that increased activity is not noticed when bauxite and ferric oxide gels are mixed mechanically. It is evident that the ferric oxide must be precipitated within the pores of the bauxite.

TABLE VI.

Adsorption by Mechanical Mixtures of Bauxite and Ferric Oxide.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Percentage composition of adsorbent :		Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
Fe_2O_3	Al_2O_3				
45.9	47.0	0.4708 g.	0.5074 g.	0.0366 g.	7.77
73.1	21.2	0.917	0.9818	0.0648	7.07

(b) *Activation of bauxite by deposition of silica gel.*—Attempts were then made to activate bauxite further by the precipitation of silica gel in place of ferric oxide, the method of preparation and activation being the same as before. The results obtained by the deposition of different quantities of silica gel are shown in the following table and the corresponding curve in Fig. IV.

Adsorption by Silicalised Bauxite.

Fig. IV.

TABLE VII.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Percentage composition of adsorbent :			Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃				
15.07	57.04	19.5	1.155 g.	1.2712 g.	0.1162 g.	10.06
29.8	47.5	18.2	1.2148	1.4081	0.1883	15.5
40.8	39.7	18.6	1.2066	1.6667	0.4581	37.9 (M ₁)
60.1	28.8	9.2	1.1966	1.526	0.3894	34.26(M ₂)
76.2	16.7	5.7	1.344	1.72	0.376	27.96(M ₃)
82.3	9.9	6.4	0.273	0.2918	0.0188	6.15

A mechanical mixture of silica and bauxite containing 48.04 per cent. of SiO₂, 38.8 per cent. of Al₂O₃, 13.28 per cent. of Fe₂O₃ was also tried under the same conditions. Its adsorption capacity was found to be only 6.65 per cent.

It is satisfactory to note from the above table that an enormous increase in adsorption capacity of bauxite may be effected by the deposition of silica, thus while bauxite and silica gel adsorb 8.42 per cent. and 9.76 per cent. respectively, the silicalised bauxite with 40.8 per cent. of SiO₂ adsorbs 37.9 per cent. The adsorption capacity of such activated bauxite for benzol at low concentration is much higher than any other inorganic adsorbent and compares favourably with activated carbon without having the defects of the latter mentioned previously. It is, however, necessary to test if this adsorbent will stand the drastic conditions prevailing in gas works and coke-ovens.

Possibility of using Silicalised Bauxite for the Recovery of Benzol from Coal Gas.

A suitable adsorbent for this purpose should naturally remain unaffected both chemically and physically when it comes in contact with coal or coke-oven gases under drastic conditions prevailing in the works and should be capable of regeneration to practically its original activity. It is now intended to study if sulphuretted hydrogen and other constituents of coal gas will have any unfavourable effect on the adsorbents and if the adsorbent exposed to tarry matter may be revived. For the purpose of these experiments, the mixed adsorbent, M₃ was used, as this mixture happened to be in stock in large amount.

Effect of Sulphuretted Hydrogen.

It was found that dry sulphuretted hydrogen when passed through the adsorbents at 26° in the usual manner was immediately oxidised and sulphur was deposited on the adsorbent, the increase in the weight of the adsorbent being 5.1 per cent. By washing the adsorbent with carbon disulphide 3.8 per cent. of free sulphur could be recovered. It will thus be observed that the adsorbent helps to purify coal gas with the recovery of free sulphur at ordinary temperature. The adsorbent was tested for sulphide and sulphate but no trace of either could be detected. The adsorbent was evidently chemically inert to the action of sulphuretted hydrogen.

In order to determine the amount of adsorbed benzol, a mixture of air, benzol, and H₂S was passed through the adsorbent until the increase in weight was practically constant. The mixture was obtained by taking H₂S from a burette at a definite rate and mixing it with air by means of a T-tube just before the latter entered the vessel containing benzol. The concentrations of benzol and H₂S were respectively 1.2 per cent. and 0.51 per cent. by volume, the actual concentration of H₂S in crude coal gas being 0.4—1.6 per cent. by volume (Rogers, "Industrial Chemistry," p. 497).

The increase in weight of the adsorbent was 24.15 per cent. as compared to 27.98 per cent. for the benzol vapour alone. It appeared that though H₂S was completely oxidised (as no smell of H₂S could be detected after adsorption), it did not materially affect the adsorption of benzol. The results of adsorption are given in Table IX.

As the adsorbent is not chemically acted upon, it may be expected that the adsorbent exposed to the action of H₂S will be capable of regeneration to almost its original strength and this has been found to be actually the case as will be evident from the following table.

TABLE VIII.

Time of roasting = 2 hrs.; other conditions same as in Table I.

Treatment of adsorbent.	Temp. of regeneration.	Initial wt.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
Roasted.	330-350°	0.698 g.	0.874 g.	0.176 g.	25.21
Washed with CS ₂ and then roasted.	400°	0.602	0.6331	0.0311	26.12
" "	490-510°	0.41	0.5236	0.1136	27.7

The Effect of Carbon Monoxide.—Carbon monoxide passed through the adsorbent M_3 , from a burette at the constant rate of 2 c.c. per minute increased the weight of the adsorbent by 1.22 per cent. only. Mixed with air and benzene vapour it was passed again through the adsorbent, the concentrations of carbon monoxide and benzol vapour being 4.4 per cent. and 1.2 per cent. by volume respectively. The increase in the weight of the adsorbent was 27.99 per cent. from which it is evident that carbon monoxide did not exercise any adverse effect on the adsorption of benzol. The results are given in Table IX.

The Effect of Ethylene.—It has been maintained by different investigators that unsaturated hydrocarbons polymerise within the pores of the adsorbent (Dunston and others, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 179t) forming sometimes tarry matter and thereby affecting the adsorption capacity. Ethylene vapour, however, did not affect the adsorbent in any such manner. Ethylene gas was collected in a large vessel over water and was passed through the adsorbent in the usual manner, the increase in weight of the adsorbent being only 1.32 per cent. Mixed with equal volume of air, ethylene was passed again through the adsorbent which increased in weight by only 0.33 per cent. The adsorbent thus exposed to the action of ethylene vapour, was heated in a current of air and the regenerated mass adsorbed 27.2 per cent. benzol. Ethylene vapour did not evidently cause any material injury to the adsorbent. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE IX.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Composition of gases.	Rate of gas flow per min.	Initial wt.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
1. Dry H_2S	... 180 c.c.	1.0489 g.	1.1023 g.	0.0535 g.	5.1
2. Dry H_2S (0.51%) benzene (1.2%) and air	... 180	0.414	0.514	0.1	24.15
3. Carbon monoxide	2	0.384	0.3897	0.0047	1.22
4. CO (4.4%) C_6H_6 (1.2%) and air	... 180	0.318	0.407	0.089	27.99
5. Ethylene	... 180	0.908	0.92	0.012	1.32
6. Ethylene and air (equal vol.)		0.2458	0.2466	0.0008	0.33

The Effect of Water Vapour.—It is important to note the effect of water vapour on the adsorbent, as the pores of many adsorbents are easily moistened by water vapour and thereby the adsorption of hydrocarbons may be prevented. Large quantities of water vapour may even wash off any benzol already adsorbed.

Air containing 3·02 per cent. water vapour by volume was passed through the adsorbent which increased by 21·6 per cent. by weight. It was therefore necessary to determine which of the two constituents, water vapour or benzol vapour was selectively adsorbed.

A mixture of water vapour (3·02 per cent. by vol.), benzol (1·2 per cent by vol.) and air was passed through the adsorbent which increased 25·82 per cent. by weight. In order to determine the proportion of water and benzol in the adsorbed mass, it was then heated in a horizontal glass tube while a dry current of air was passed through. The water vapour in the escaping gas was absorbed by means of calcium chloride tubes. The increase in weight was due to 4·8 per cent. of water and 21·02 per cent. of benzol.

It will be seen that water vapour itself does not lower the absorption to a very great extent though it must be remembered (Williams, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 97r.) that long continued passage of the gas containing water vapour may ultimately wash off the absorbed benzol. It is necessary to stop the passage of the gas mixture at a suitable moment after an hour or two when the proportion of benzol in the adsorbent is the greatest.

Effect of tarry Matter on Regeneration of the Adsorbent.—The adsorbent M_3 was soaked with a little tar subjected to roasting in a current of dry air. The absorption capacity of the regenerated mass is shown in the following table.

TABLE X.
Conditions same as Table I.

Temp. of roasting.	Initial wt. of adsorbent.	Final wt. of adsorbent.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
300-310°	0·2378 g.	0·2672 g.	0·0294 g.	12·36
420-430°	0·1258	0·1523	0·0265	21·07
540-560°	0·541	0·6877	0·1467	27·12

It will be observed that it is necessary to heat the adsorbent to higher temperature (540-560°) to recover its original activity, as the carbonaceous matter in the pores must be completely burnt off,

The unchanged activity of the adsorbent indicates that it is not changed by subjecting it to the above temperature.

Effect of Temperature on Adsorption.—In order to determine the efficiency of the adsorbent M_2 , under different climatic conditions, its activity was determined at three different temperatures, 19°, 26° and 35°. The efficiencies of adsorption are noted below.

TABLE XI.

Conditions (excepting temp. of the thermostat) same as in Table I.

Temp.	Initial wt.	Final wt.	Increase of wt.	Percentage of adsorption.
19°	0.21 g.	0.2884 g.	0.0764 g.	37.33
26°	0.32	0.4293	0.1093	34.16
35°	0.1101	0.1355	0.0254	23.07

Discussion.

It will be observed from the above experiments that silicified bauxite is eminently suitable for the adsorption of benzol vapour. The above figures have been obtained with the adsorbent M_3 , but much higher figures would be obtained by using the adsorbent M_1 , which adsorbs 37.9 per cent. of benzol in comparison with 27.98 per cent. by M_3 . The advantages of using this adsorbent in preference to others, have already been indicated. The following considerations will show that it is also preferable to adsorption by wash-oil which is generally used.

It is well known that the benzol obtained by wash-oil process is highly coloured and is mixed with "prebenzol" as well as with lighter fractions of creosote which is used as wash-oil. The wash-oil benzol has therefore to be subjected to long continued fractionation before it can be used even as motor-spirit. It has been shown by Williams (*loc. cit.*) that the benzol obtained by the adsorption process is good in colour and requires little or no fractionation. It further requires no washing with sulphuric acid (as in the case of wash-oil benzol) which naturally destroys a considerable fraction of the benzol. The yield of benzol by the adsorption process is therefore quite satisfactory.

It may also be noted that the adsorbent or the wash-oil as the case may be, has to be heated to at least 120-140° to drive

off the crude benzol (containing toluene and xylene) and subsequently cooled to ordinary temperature. As alumina has a very low specific heat, the quantity of heat used in the above process should therefore be small in comparison with that required for wash-oil process.

It may further be observed that silicalised bauxite adsorbs 37.9 per cent. while wash-oil only 3—4 per cent. of benzol. To recover the same quantity of benzol, a large quantity of wash-oil has therefore to be heated in comparison with silicalised bauxite. The use of the adsorption process should therefore cause a saving in the cost of fuel. Further, as the benzol may be obtained in fairly good quality and may be used direct for motor-spirit, the cost of rectification even for pure benzol would be considerably less than that in the wash-oil process.

Summary.

(1) It has been observed that the mixed adsorbents formed by simultaneous precipitation of two or more adsorbents or by precipitation of one adsorbent within the pores of the other have very high adsorption capacity for benzol vapour. The amount of increase in adsorption depends on suitable proportion of different ingredients of the mixed adsorbents and on the nature of those ingredients.

(2) The enhanced activity of bauxite as an adsorbent has been explained by the fact of its being a natural mixed adsorbent.

(3) The adsorption capacity of bauxite for benzol vapour has been enormously increased (from 8.42 to 37.9 per cent.) by deposition of silica gel.

(4) This silicalised bauxite has been tested under different conditions similar to those prevailing in gas-works and coke-ovens and has been found suitable. It is not changed either chemically or physically under the action of different ingredients of coal gas and may be regenerated by the simple process of roasting in the air, to almost its original activity.

(5) The advantages of the use of silicalised bauxite in place of wash-oil is shortly discussed.

In conclusion, we beg to offer our best thanks to the Director of Geological Survey, Calcutta, for placing some samples of Indian bauxite at our disposal for the purpose of these investigations.